

α -Picoline Complexes of the Fluoborates of Nickel And Cobalt. Part I

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α -Picoline complexes of fluoborates of nickel and cobalt have been prepared and their properties and composition determined. The stability of nickel and cobalt complexes has been studied on the basis of heat of dissociation, pressure-composition isothermals, heat of formation, lattice energy of complex, entropy functions, and free energy of the system. The results show that the stability of a complex does not depend on any one of the physical parameters considered separately.

As hardly any reference on the preparation and stability of α -picoline complexes of nickel and cobalt fluoborates could be found in the literature, it was considered of interest to prepare α -picoline complexes of nickel and cobalt and study their stabilities, employing different methods. The results of these studies are reported herein.

EXPERIMENTAL

The fluoboric acid was prepared according to Gmelin and Kraut¹. The fluoborates of nickel and cobalt were prepared in the laboratory by adding pure carbonates of nickel and cobalt to a fluoboric acid solution with a slight excess of the acid and the solution was crystallised. The solution must contain a little excess of fluoboric acid so as to avoid the association of free F^- ions. Their composition agrees to $M(BF_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ ($M=Co$ or Ni). The fluoborates are deliquescent.

The fluoborates being insoluble in α -picoline, a saturated solution of the fluoborate in anhydrous ethanol was added dropwise to a freshly distilled α -picoline, kept in a r.b. flask with constant stirring on a water bath. After 6-7hr., the content was allowed to cool; needle-shaped crystals separating were filtered through suction, pressed, and dried in a desiccator (H_2SO_4).

The fluoboric acid was estimated as nitron-fluoborate². A modified method was followed by dissolving the complex in water (100 ml) with glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and to this ice-cooled solution ($5-7^\circ$) a cold solution ($5-7^\circ$) of nitron in acetic acid (2.5%) was added dropwise with constant stirring till the crystalline precipitate appeared. The precipitate was kept for 6 hr. at 10° and then filtered through a weighed sintered glass crucible; it was washed with cold water ($5-7^\circ$) for 4-5 times, dried at 110° in an air-oven, and weighed. The percentage and corresponding formulas of the complexes are recorded in Table I.

1. "Handbuch der anorganischen Chemie", 1930, Vol. VIII, p. 115.

2. Lange, *Ber.*, 1868, 21, 579.

3. Vogel, 'A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', 3rd ed., 1961, p. 578, Longmans, London.

TABLE I

	Ni(BF ₄) ₂ · 4 α-picoline.		Co(BF ₄) ₂ · 4 α-picoline.	
	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
Metal	9.60 %	9.61 %	9.65 %	9.75 %
BF ₄	29.54	28.71	28.80	28.72
α-Picoline	60.86	61.68	61.54	61.53

The complexes of nickel and cobalt are light green and pink in colour respectively; these are hygroscopic, soluble in water, insoluble in benzene, cyclohexanone, and acetone. The nickel complex is more hygroscopic than that of cobalt.

Pressure-composition Isothermals.—The apparatus used for the measurements of dissociation pressure and pressure-composition isothermals was of the type described by Ray and Sinha⁴ and it was set at 60°. Determination of pressure-composition isothermals at a temperature below 60° did not show much loss in α-picoline. Attempts to work above 60° had to be abandoned as the compounds tended to decomposition at higher temperatures. The results are shown in Table II and the isothermal curves for nickel and cobalt co-ordination compounds are shown in Fig. 1 and 2.

TABLE II

Pressure-composition isothermals.

Pressure.	Loss of α-picoline (No. of moles).	Moles α-picoline/ M atom.	Pressure.	Loss of α-picoline (No. of moles).	Moles α-picoline/ M atom.
Co(BF ₄) ₂ · 4 α-picoline.					
Ni(BF ₄) ₂ · 4 picoline.					
7.76 mm	0.2	4.0	1.58 mm	0.1	2.0
7.76	0.3	3.8	1.58	..	1.9
7.76	0.5	3.5	1.58	0.1	1.9
3.68	0.4	3.0	1.58	0.2	1.8
3.68	0.1	2.8			
3.68	0.5	2.5	1.58	0.1	1.6
3.68	0.5	2.0	1.58	..	1.5
11.70	0.3	4.0	6.14	0.2	2.2
11.70	0.3	3.7	1.50	0.1	2.0
11.70	0.3	3.4	1.50	0.1	1.9
11.70	0.1	3.1	1.50	0.5	1.8
6.14	0.2	3.0	1.50	1.3	1.3
6.14	0.6	2.8	1.50	..	1.3

M=Ni or Co.

Dissociation Pressure and Heat of Dissociation.—The dissociation pressures of the complexes were measured at different temperatures, using the same apparatus as described above. The logarithm of pressure was plotted against reciprocal of absolute temperature and from the slope of the linear graphs, heat of dissociation, Δ*H*, of the complex was calculated according to the Clapeyron-Clausius equation. The results obtained are recorded in Table III and graphically represented in Fig. 3.

FIG. 2. Isothermal of $\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4$ picoline.

Determination of Heat of Formation

The heats of formation of these complexes were directly determined by thermochemical measurements, using Dewar flask type of calorimeter, a slow-moving stirrer, and a Beckmann thermometer. The correction of heat due to stirrer and radiation was made. The heats of reactions of $\text{Ni}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4$ picol. and $\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4$ picol. in $3N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ were determined.

TABLE III
Heat of dissociation of the complexes.

Temp.	Pressure.	$10^6 T$.	$\log_{10} P$.	Mean ΔH (kcal./mole α -picoline).	Temp.	Pressure.	$10^6 T$.	$\log_{10} P$.	Mean ΔH (kcal./mole α -picoline).
System: $\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 4/3 \alpha$ -picoline.									
45.5°	2.85 mm	3139	0.4548		50.5°	3.65	3091	0.5026	
50.6°	4.70	3091	0.6721		52.8°	4.08	3070	0.6109	
52.8°	5.83	3070	0.7656	20.85	55.5°	4.65	3049	0.6675	12.07
55.0°	7.27	3049	0.8615		57.5°	5.44	3021	0.7356	
60.0°	11.70	3003	1.0682		60.0°	6.14	3003	0.7882	
System: $\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 2/0 \alpha$ -picoline.									
60.0°	1.50	3003	0.1761		43.5°	1.82	3159	0.2610	
62.6°	2.47	2980	0.3930		52.5°	4.01	3073	0.6031	
64.5°	3.16	2968	0.4997	42.31	56.4°	5.60	3035	0.7554	18.51
66.0°	4.68	2950	0.6705		60.0°	7.76	3003	0.8000	
68.5°	6.38	2935	0.8046		61.4°	8.71	2900	0.9401	
					65.0°	11.92	2939	0.2000	
System: $\text{Ni}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot 3/2 \alpha$ -picoline.									
56.4°	2.03	3035	0.3601		60.0°	1.58	3003	0.1087	
57.0°	2.46	3031	0.3007		61.4°	1.70	2900	0.2360	
60.0°	3.68	3003	0.5659	20.35	63.6°	1.00	2973	0.2700	13.43
61.4°	4.46	2900	0.6510		68.8°	2.90	2928	0.4180	
65.0°	7.09	2959	0.8906		70.0°	2.82	3010	0.4501	

FIG. 3
Curves I—VI refer respectively to Ni (BF₄)₂. 4/3 pico., Ni (BF₄)₂. 3/2 pico., Ni (BF₄)₂. 2 pico., Co(BF₄)₂. 4/3 pico., Co(BF₄)₂. 3/2 pico., and Co(BF₄)₂. 2 pico.

The heats of formation were calculated by the application of Hess's law of heat summation.

(where M = Ni and Co).

Q could not be determined experimentally and hence evaluated from the following considerations. The anhydrous salt could not be prepared and heat of solution could not be measured experimentally. Heats of solution of anhydrous nickel and cobalt fluoroborates were calculated from Fajan's formula:

$$L = Wh^{2+} + Wh^{-} - U$$

L is the heat of solution; Wh²⁺ and Wh⁻ are heats of hydration of cations and anions and U is the lattice energy. These values are evaluated from the application of the formula of Yatsimirskii⁵ and Kapustiniskii⁶. The heats of hydration of Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, and BF₄⁻ are 447.29, 408.7, and 5.4 kcal./g. ion respectively. The corresponding lattice energies of the simple salts as calculated from Kapustiniskii's formula⁶ had been evaluated to 445.39 and 401.2 kcal. respectively. The heats of solution of anhydrous nickel and cobalt fluoroborates according to Fajan's formula were found to be 109.9 and 115.6 kcal./mole. The heats of solution of Ni(BF₄)₂·6H₂O and Co(BF₄)₂·6H₂O were experimentally found to be 2.312 and 1.4086 kcal./mole respectively. From the algebraic summation of the two steps, one involv-

5. *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 4809.

6. *Ibid.*, 1934, 28, 4955.

ing heat of solution of the anhydrous salt and the second, heat of solution of hydrated salt, Q , was calculated and found to 107.588 and 114.09 kcal./g. mole for nickel and cobalt fluoborate respectively. Putting these values of Q in the original equation, the heats of formation for nickel and cobalt complexes were found to be 60.242 and 77.616 kcal./g. mole respectively.

TABLE IV

Average value of thermal capacity of the apparatus with 168.9 ml of 3N-H₂SO₄ soln. (40.9 cal./°C).

Substance.	Weight.	Rise in temp. (corr.)	Heat of reaction (G.F.W.) mean value (k cal.).	Heat of formation per G. F. W. (value of Q con- sidered; k cal.).
Ni(BF ₄) ₂ .4 pico.	0.2489 g.	+ 0.18°	..	60.242
	0.5001	+0.36°	90.57(q_3)	
	1.0100	+0.71°		
Co(BF ₄) ₂ .4 pico.	0.8927	+0.55°	76.1477 (q_3)	77.616
	0.8001	+0.49°		
	0.7912	+0.48°		
Ni(BF ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	0.7167	+0.03°	2.984 (q_1)	..
	0.6727	+0.025°		
	0.0838	+0.027°		
Co(BF ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	0.9961	+0.02°	1.434 (q_1)	..
	0.9832	+0.02°		
	0.8990	+0.018°		
α -Picoline	1.5120	1.008°	10060 (q_2)	..
	1.6710	1.148°		
	2.1210	1.455°		

Lattice Energy of the Complexes.—Blitz and Grim⁷ have shown that complex formation is closely connected with the nature of the crystal-lattice energy of the compound forming the complex. They found that the lattice energy of the ammoniates was the sum of the lattice energy of the ammonia-free salt and the heat formation of the ammoniates. Lattice energies of Ni and Co fluoborates, as calculated from the formula of Kapustiniskii⁶, have been mentioned previously. So the lattice energies of 4, 3, and 2 picoline complexes of nickel come to 463.90, 474.74, and 458.82 kcal./g. mole respectively and similarly those for cobalt are 422.05, 413.27, and 443.51 kcal./g. mole respectively.

Free Energy and Entropy Changes of the Complexes.—The free-energy changes are calculated from the well-known thermodynamic equation: •

$$G = RT \log_e \frac{P_2}{P_1}$$

P_1 and P_2 standing for vapour pressure of α -picoline and equilibrium pressures of complex salts at temperature T . On evaluation with the respective data, the three systems:

4/3 pico., 3/2 pico., and 2/0 pico. come for cobalt complex to 1.256, 1.592, and 1.863 kcal./g. mole respectively at 60° and for nickel complex, 1.528, 1.683, and 2.681 kcal./g. mole respectively at 60°.

The entropy changes are calculated from the equation:

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

where ΔH = heat of dissociation, ΔG = the free-energy changes, and ΔS = the entropy term.

From previous evaluation of ΔH , ΔG , and ΔS , the three systems of cobalt complexes for the system 4/3, 3/2, and 2/0 are found to be 58.81, 31.46, and 121.46 e.u. at 60°, whereas those for nickel come to 50.99, 83.06, and 32.88 e.u. at 60° respectively.

DISCUSSION

Previous workers⁸ have shown that complexes of a cation with the lowest number of ligand molecules are much more stable than those with the highest number of co-ordinating groups. This behaviour has been supported by the heat of dissociation data. But the present investigation has definitely shown the anomalous behaviour of nickel from the consideration of heat of dissociation data. Although cobalt complex is agreeing with the previous contention, corresponding 2/0 systems of nickel complexes have shown lowest value for ΔH . This sort of anomalous behaviour of the complexes had also been observed by Bhattacharya and Sinha⁹ and Davis *et al.*¹⁰, who found that complexes with the lowest number of ligand molecules were not the most stable.

In order to explain the irregularity, help has been taken of other experimentally determined thermodynamical data, e.g. lattice energy, free energy, and entropy changes of the complexes. It is generally accepted that the lattice energy of different ammoniates increases with the decrease in the number of ammonia molecules. There is no doubt that the same explanation holds when ammonia molecules are replaced by molecules of pyridine, α -picoline, quinoline, etc. The values of lattice energy for the three co-ordination number, 4, 3, and 2, for nickel are discrete and not in agreement with the previously accepted principle. The same deviation is marked between 4 and 3 picoline complexes of cobalt. Similarly, no clue is furnished by the data on entropy functions of different systems of the said complexes—the discrete nature of experimental values fails to suggest the order of stability just like the values of heat of dissociation and lattice energy.

If free-energy changes of a system is considered to be a measure of chemical affinity between the reactants, the complex with the lowest number of ligand molecules should be most stable. Experimentally determined data on free-energy changes of cobalt and nickel, 4-, 3-, and 2-, co-ordinated complexes fully confirm this contention. So, in all probability, out of all the thermodynamical data, the true measure of stability of co-ordination compounds

8. Blitz *et al.*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1919, 109, 89; 1923, 129, 1, 14.

9. *This Journal*, 1955, 32, 414.

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4089; 1934, 56, 106.

in solid phase might be the measure of free-energy changes. The present investigation with other cations and β - and γ -picolines is being pursued to establish the utility of determination of free-energy changes to assess the order of the stability of co-ordination compounds.

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